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When and under what circumstances should welfare policy support low-income entrepreneurs?

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Executive summary

Low income is relatively common in self-employment, forcing policymakers to consider when, and under what circumstances, they should support struggling entrepreneurs. In this policy brief, we propose a conceptual framework of six key causes of low profit in entrepreneurship. We call upon welfare researchers and policymakers to examine their welfare policies to determine which causes of low income they currently support through income top-ups and to identify gaps in support. As welfare policy for the self-employed has historically been developed as an 'add on' to welfare policy for employment, it may be timely to reflect on the social and economic value of somewhat accidental policy positions and to recognise welfare as an important form of entrepreneurial finance.

Introduction

Recent Entrepreneurship Policy and Practice Insights (Marlow, 2023; Henry, 2024) have illustrated that self-employment is a potentially precarious form of work. Before the Covid-19 pandemic, self-employment had been on the rise in many countries (e.g., Statistisches Bundesamt, 2020) and in the UK it was at an all-time high (Clark, 2022) and "a distinguishing feature of the UK labour market's recovery from the last recession" (CIPD, 2018: 5). While many solo self-employed individuals enjoy significant freedoms, they also shoulder entrepreneurial risks and incomes from self-employment had fallen dramatically, as incomes increased (Giupponi and Xu, 2020). In the UK, and internationally, governments face the dilemma of when (or whether) to compensate for low income in self-employment through welfare systems (Rouse et al., 2021). Yet, with a few notable exceptions, (e.g. Danson et al., 2021; Caraher and Reuter,

2019; Rouse, 2007), the entrepreneurship community has ignored the welfare system as an institutional context, and source of financial capital, for entrepreneurship. This creates a significant barrier to shaping evidence-informed and just enterprise ecosystems and inhibits our ability to inform the Sustainable Development Goal of creating “decent work” (Somavia, 1999) through self-employment.

Low income may be common at certain stages of the business life course (e.g. start-up) and during global or personal crises (e.g. Covid-19 or ill health), or it may relate to wider factors in personal and business lives, affecting some groups more than others. Policymakers need thinking tools to confront this complexity and decide when, under what circumstances, and to what extent (or for how long) they should use welfare systems to top-up low incomes. This Insights brief offers a framework to structure analysis and we hope it will foster useful policy debate.

Theoretical framework

Welfare theorists commonly use the term ‘decommodification’ to analyse and distinguish forms of welfare policy (Esping-Andersen, 1990). Decommodification was advanced to articulate the extent to which a society endows citizens with an acceptable standard of living independent of their market participation. The idea behind decommodification is that a state may seek to financially support people whose ability to undertake employment labour is restricted by their health, age or care commitments, because they cannot find work or should have the freedom to choose the work they undertake. Policymakers must decide on the circumstances they will decommodify labour.

When we started to work with the concept of decommodification in relation to entrepreneurship we realised that it may relate to having, or using, restricted entrepreneurial labour, a key entrepreneurial resource that is widely under-recognised (Rouse and Jayawarna, 2017). Yet, welfare support may also be needed when entrepreneur labour is high, but the entrepreneurial process of combining resources into goods and services under conditions of uncertainty with the hope of profitable trade (Kitching and Rouse, 2016) produces low or no profits, or even losses. In this case, policymakers offering income top-ups would be decommodifying the entrepreneurial process. In her PhD thesis, Weicht (2023) conceptualises how welfare responses to low income in entrepreneurship may decommodify entrepreneur labour, the entrepreneurial process, or a combination of these, but in different ways. Below, we share six key causes of low income from entrepreneurship under these three headings, and hope this will enable welfare policymakers to think more clearly about the form of entrepreneurial dilemma they are supporting (or choose not to support). We also briefly outline the welfare policy dilemma suggested in each case.

We are conscious that entrepreneurs live in mixed economies and work in a hybrid way (Kneiding and Kritikos, 2013) and so may not be entirely dependent on entrepreneurship for their household or personal income. The following analysis confines itself to thinking about causes of low income within entrepreneurship and the rising policy dilemmas. That broader complexity is an important topic for further conceptualisation.

Lastly, we acknowledge that welfare responses occur in socio-cultural and ecological contexts and that these also shape political responses to low incomes in entrepreneurship. To demonstrate this, we consider how global or local crises may create particular circumstances for policy response and, so, discuss how our framework can inform our retrospective sensemaking around Covid-19 policy and consideration of current or future crises (such as natural disasters, climate change, fuel or cost of living crises etc). Equally, we consider how policy responses may also depend on broader political ideas about the role of entrepreneurship and welfare systems in the functioning of society, and the fiscal positions of different states. In short, we relate policy responses to the concept of decommodification as this relates to political economies.

Six causes of low-income self-employment and their respective welfare policy dilemmas

Set A: Causes relating to the availability of entrepreneur labour

Causes 1 and 2 (below) are more akin to the dilemmas that welfare policymakers typically face in relation to employment. That is, when to compensate for the restricted availability of employment labour. They arise due to the 'need' to decommodify entrepreneurial labour.

1. **An entrepreneur may choose not to invest their labour in full to preserve leisure time.** They may trade at low or no profit because they are voluntarily using their labour for leisure pursuits. We can here think of someone who pursues a hobby, such as surfing or making artwork. The surfer or artist may voluntarily decommodify their labour: they forgo income for the sake of more free time to surf or to create art that they do not plan to sell or which they do not reasonably expect to sell for a profit that would reward the labour invested in it. The welfare policy question that arises from such a cause of low profit is whether it is a citizen's right to be supported via welfare if they make these choices? Are there some leisure activities that have social value that the state would choose to support (e.g. voluntary work that offsets public spending or creative endeavours that create wider social good)? And, if so, to what extent, for how long and to which groups should welfare support be granted?
2. **An entrepreneur may be unable to invest their labour (in full) because they need to use it to conduct unpaid care work.** Here, policy needs to consider whether to support entrepreneurs who can only trade part-time because they are conducting socially valuable care work or whether to improve the care infrastructure to liberate entrepreneurs from their care work. They may choose to make entrepreneurs absorb the cost of care labour, without support.

Set B: Causes relating to low, no or negative profit from the entrepreneurial process

Causes 3-5 are different to the dilemmas normally faced by welfare policymakers as low income does not relate to the restricted availability of labour but to mechanisms within the entrepreneurial process (the combination of resources into goods and services and the attempt to sell these at a profit). They arise from the decommodification of the entrepreneurial process.

Cause 5 – low income arising from the temporary absence of a market – is somewhat akin to a more familiar welfare problem: low demand for labour.

3. **An entrepreneur may invest their labour fully in their entrepreneurial process and but still not achieve sufficient profit to draw a reasonable income.** This might occur due to problems at different stages of the entrepreneurial process. The entrepreneur may be trading in a good or service without sufficient financial value relative to the cost of resources; have misjudged the market, or the market may have changed, or; be trading with a (reasonable) hope for future profit. Here, policymakers may want to distinguish these circumstances and provide support to trade in a sufficiently valuable good or service, understand a market better or otherwise adapt their business to make better profits (e.g. by buying cheaper resources, using fewer resources or combining resources into goods and services more efficiently). Alternatively, policymakers may need to consider if the entrepreneur's hope of profit is reasonable and for how long the entrepreneur should be supported while they await a return. In any of these cases, the need for welfare assistance to top-up low income may be matched by a need for financial investment in the entrepreneurial process; while income supplements support the supply of entrepreneurial labour, the business may need investments of non-labour resources and support to combine resources into goods and services more efficiently, or with better hope of a timely profitable return.
4. **An entrepreneur may be providing goods or services profitably but will only get paid in the future, or they may be suffering late payment.** Here, welfare policymakers may need to consider if they should help with a cash flow or late-payment problem by providing a grant or loan to top-up income in the short-term and to sustain the wider entrepreneurial process. This dilemma may be common during start-up or during a phase of fast growth and policymakers may choose to design policy specific to these phases of the business life course. Investment in maintaining the business process (buying resources, producing and selling goods and services) may be required, as well as topping up entrepreneur income.
5. **An entrepreneur may experience a temporary absence of a market.** This may be for various reasons from the highly predictable (e.g. seasonal trade) to unforeseen crises such as a global pandemic (for a detailed critique of the UK's Self-Employment Income Support Scheme, see Rouse et al., 2021). The policy question here is what kind of market disruption should be supported. Policy aims may be to sustain businesses, so they support trade and, possibly, growth following a market downturn. Welfare policymakers also need to consider what seasonal work they want to subsidise (e.g. to protect a local economy dependent on tourism or to support a 'reserve army' of agricultural workers). The policy question partly relates to risk: some risks are knowable, e.g. for seasonal workers, while others may not be, e.g., a crisis situation, and some relate to wider risks (e.g. food security or local economic decline). The question a welfare state could consider is what kind of risks the state is prepared to manage by providing welfare support to the low-income entrepreneur. As in Causes 3 and 4, investment may be required in

sustaining business operations as well as topping up entrepreneur income. Policymakers may also support policies such as diversification or hybridity (e.g. combining self-employment and employment) to offset the risk of low income from entrepreneurship.

Set C: A cause related to investing entrepreneurial labour and/or other resources in goods and services with high social value but low economic value

Cause 6 produces low income through a combination of investing at least some entrepreneurial labour in low or non-profit making activity (akin to Causes 1 and 2) while still deploying that labour to create value, but struggling to realise that value economically (akin to Causes 3-5). It arises from the decommodification of entrepreneurial labour and the entrepreneurial process.

6. **An entrepreneur may invest their labour and other resources in producing a good or service with social value and cannot achieve a sufficient profit to draw a decent income while also producing that social value;** for example, an entrepreneur who produces social, cultural, environmental, or other value, but does not produce economic value because they are not motivated to sell their goods and services or because the market is unwilling to pay a price that would garner a reasonable profit. Here, welfare policy would need to consider which types of non-economic value it is prepared to invest in by supplementing the incomes of the low-income self-employed. This policy dilemma is somewhat analogous to the question of whether to support volunteer work through welfare supplements.

In each of the six key causes, welfare policymakers face dilemmas that are additional to considering whether they wish to decommodify entrepreneurial labour and/or the entrepreneurial process in particular ways. They must decide which of the self-employed they will support (e.g. which social group or occupation), in which kinds of households (e.g. whether to take a household view of income or whether to protect children whose parents pursue low-income self-employment), at what stage of the business, personal and family life cycles (e.g. during start-up or growth, when young or old, or when making a career transition such as leaving the armed forces or following retirement, or to support young families), to what extent (e.g. assessing the amount of income subsidy) and for how long (e.g. supporting short-term or longer-term decommodification).

Economists remind us that government investments can produce wider externalities, and should not be thought of like household purses, and so macro-economic effects must be considered, as must non-economic goals such as sustainability. Ultimately, of course, welfare policies are political decisions and politicians need to be able to justify changes to the electorate who may keenly observe whether decommodification is equitable for the employed and self-employed. Policy ought, also, to take a longer-term view; it may justify supporting business exit where long-term trends make profitability unlikely. This demands insight into markets and business that the 'street-level bureaucrats' administering welfare policy may lack; this is an important research and policy innovation direction.

Policymakers may also choose to address the underlying causes of low income in entrepreneurship. These relate to access to resources and markets, the human and social capital required to combine resources into goods and services and the process of achieving profitable sales. For example, Cause 2 relates to the scarcity of entrepreneurial labour caused by weak care infrastructures, Cause 3 might be resolved through business support, and Cause 4 arises in part from regulations and weak enforcement processes that permit late payment. Nevertheless, there is an urgent need for welfare policymakers specifically to consider the logic of their response to low income in entrepreneurship and to understand the complexity of this policy problem.

We hope this paper “reveals” welfare systems as institutions that shape entrepreneurial action and enterprise ecosystems. We have developed a multi-axis framework of conditions that may cause entrepreneurs to need welfare support and related this to three forms of decommodification. We hope this can enable policymakers to consider the circumstances in which the welfare state may or may not support particular entrepreneurs suffering low income.

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